

ORGANIZATION OF STUDENTS' ACTIVITIES IN LITERATURE LESSONS USING A SYSTEM OF LEARNING TASKS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14413714>

Аннотация

В данной статье подчеркивается, что содержательная сторона системы основана на текстах различных жанров, а организационная – на инновационной деятельности, и наш опыт показывает, что она будет интересна и эффективна для современных школьников. Для решения поставленных задач описывается организация деятельности учащихся на занятиях по литературному чтению с использованием системы учебных задач.

Ключевые слова: учебный процесс, интерпретация, исследование, проектирование, задачи, процесс, учебные задачи, учебник, практика.

Annotation

This article emphasizes that the content side of the system based on texts of various genres, and the organizational side based on innovative activities, and our experience shows that it will be interesting and effective for modern schoolchildren. To solve the set tasks, the organization of students' activities described in the classes on literary reading using the system of educational tasks.

Key words: learning process, interpretation, research, design, tasks, process, learning tasks, textbook, practice.

Introduction. It is possible to organize students' activities at the lessons of literary reading using the system of educational tasks on literary reading that we have developed. The content side of the system based on texts of various genres, and the organizational side based on innovative activities (research, interpretation, and project, creative, game). In order to use the task system in the learning process, it is necessary to make it convenient and effective. It is necessary to take into account the need for space for the student's problem-solving activities. For example, a student has to highlight parts of the text, mark the correct answers in hints, draw text and pictures and even cut them out to manipulate them. Therefore, in our opinion, the most appropriate form of

educational task system will be a workbook for literary reading. Educational tools of this type actively used in school practice. The workbook considered by researchers as a special teaching aid, in particular the problems of its development and the effectiveness of implementation. It is necessary to take into account this experience, as well as to generalize the modern requirements for this type of benefits.

Researchers have not addressed the issues of competence development through workbooks, nor have they studied the modern, latest requirements of the state educational standard for these textbooks. Therefore, it is necessary to determine how the goals and strategies of the new standards affect the content and structure of literary reading textbooks aimed at competence development.

The author should suggest types of collective work that develop communicative general learning activities of schoolchildren. - A modern schoolchild studying at school should have the ability to work together: to take into account the opinion of partners, to form their own position, to negotiate, to ask questions and to make clear statements to the partner. This means that the manual should present the work done independently, as well as in the framework of educational cooperation: in pairs, in groups.

The choice of works for creating educational tasks is determined by the following factors:

- taking into account the age characteristics of modern schoolchildren and their interest in learning;
- consideration of thematic and genre diversity.

When selecting fiction texts, we gave preference to examples that evoke an emotional response, are understandable to children and make them want to read the text in full, if it is given in fragments. Teaching tasks are based on various texts: folklore (legends, fairy tales, riddles, proverbs, languages) and fantasy stories, from classical Uzbek literature to modern children's literature. Uzbek literature, literature of brotherly nations and foreign literature by Abdullah Kahkhor, Gafur Gulam, Adil Yagubov, Otkir Hashimov, Alisher Navoi, Abay, Avaz O'tar, Langston Hughes, Khodjiakbar Shaikhov, Ray Bradbury, Jules Verne, Arthur Conan Doyle and other writers and poets. The notebooks contain works by contemporary authors. As can be seen from the above, the main area of reading is local literature, although foreign literature is also represented.

Some texts are given without abbreviations; these are poems, fairy tales and short stories. Large volumes of work cannot be fully incorporated into the format of the assignment, as the main area of it is for the child's work - for

questions and tasks. If we were to use only short works without abbreviations, it would immediately narrow the range of artistic works. That is why some texts are given as a large part of the work. Working on the work creates additional opportunities for the child's development: the pupil is forced to control the time, place of action and background of events regardless of the context.

When selecting works of art, it was necessary to take into account thematic diversity so that each pupil could find his/her "niche" and reading preferences. Texts about family, friendship, school life are close to children, and they are happy to discuss these topics. Therefore, the stories were presented. We chose works related to the "higher" themes: About the Motherland (including about the small motherland, about the roots of man), About the Earth (environmental texts and lyrical works about beauty). We paid special attention to the theme of patriotism and tried to present it delicately, lyrically and sincerely. This was possible thanks to the literary texts "Walls of Motherland" by Khurshid Davron, "Praised Paths" by Ibraim Yusupov, "Soulful Motherland" by Hamza Hakimzad Niyazi, "Knowledge of Motherland" by Sirodjiddin Syed.

School-age children are keen to read books about animals, so we gave the pupils an opportunity to reflect on the theme of responsibility to those they teach.

The reading circle of schoolchildren has always included folklore works. We have changed the traditional view of studying fairy tales as a conflict of good and evil to a more modern one with elements of research. In textbooks, the fairy tale considered from the point of view of its historical roots. The author's fairy tale compared with folk tales. The logic of this comparison is clear even to a young student. Masters of words use the achievements of folk art in their works. Oscar Wilde's fairy tales allowed to identify the heritage of folklore and at the same time showed the originality of the author's handwriting.

Some teaching tasks based on artistic-analytical tasks, thanks to which a young pupil can compare artistic texts and scientific texts, feel and identify the peculiarities of the artistic word. The variety of text topics and their high aesthetic value aroused students' interest in reading, became a source for each reader to search for his or her reading circle and favorite authors in the world of books. It is a step towards the development of reading skills such as good reading and the ability to act while reading.

In the workbook, important content elements are crosswords, tables, graphic illustrations, Venn diagrams, and various methods. All the visuals created by the creator of the workbook are "working", i.e. the pictures

participate in the tasks, suggest the correct answer and help to understand the issues at hand.

The goal of the first group is not just to describe content, but to help solve a learning problem through visuals. For example, in the study comparing scientific and artistic texts, the drawings for the texts are “quick”: dictionaries, work with an explanatory dictionary, illustrated scientific journals, a fragment of a scientific text about the Moon, an artistic text, illustrated with a beautiful night scene. The main purpose of the work is to compare folk and author's fairy tales. The picture drawn for a modern fairy tale shows a cityscape described in the text of the fairy tale. It clear from the picture that the text belongs to the author, and the details of modern life cannot told in folk tales.

With the help of images, attention, the ability to analyze and compare verbal and visual information is developed. For example, based on Bloom's taxonomy, the reinforcement of Oscar Wilde's fairy tale “The Happy Prince” considered. According to this, students have steps such as knowledge, understanding, practical application, analysis, synthesis and creativity.

Conclusion. Thus, pictures to texts help to deep learning of the teaching material. Due to this interactive method, first, a good methodical preparation before the lesson is required from the teacher. In addition, students will have to read and understand the text very carefully. In this case, depending on how much students perceive the text, they master the learning according to the intended level.

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